

Catalog of Perspectives and Concerns

ML objectives:

Bridging the gap between the high-level goals and detailed properties of ML models is one of the most common causes of failure. Success in ML-enabled systems is hard to define with a single metric. One good practice is to define success at different levels.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Problem & Context</i>	the problem that ML will address and its context before coding. ML must be targeted at the right problem.
<i>Organizational goals</i>	measurable benefits ML is expected to bring to the organization. <i>E.g.</i> , increase the revenue in X%, increase the number of units sold in Y%, number of trees saved.
<i>User goals</i>	what the users want to achieve by using ML. <i>E.g.</i> , for recommendation systems this could involve helping users find content they will enjoy.
<i>Model goals</i>	metrics and acceptable measures the model should achieve (<i>e.g.</i> , for classification problems this could involve accuracy > X%, precision > Y%, recall > Z%).
<i>Leading indicators</i>	measures correlating with future success, from the business' perspective. This could include the users' affective states when using the ML-enabled system (<i>e.g.</i> , customer sentiment and engagement).
<i>ML functionality</i>	the ML results in terms of functionality that the model will provide (<i>e.g.</i> , classify customers, predict probabilities).
<i>ML trade-off</i>	the balance of customer expectations (<i>e.g.</i> , inference time vs accuracy, false positive vs false negative).

User Experience

A good ML-enabled system includes building better experiences of using ML. The goal of this perspective is to present the predictions of the model to users in a way that achieves the system objectives and to gather user feedback to improve the model.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Accountability</i>	who is responsible for unexpected model results or actions taken based on unexpected model results.
<i>Cost</i>	the costs involved in executing the inferences and also the user impact of a wrong model prediction.
<i>Forcefulness</i>	how strongly the system forces the user to do what the model indicates they should (e.g., automatic or assisted actions).
<i>Frequency</i>	how often the system interacts with users (e.g., interact whenever the user asks for it or whenever the system thinks the user will respond).
<i>Interactiveness</i>	what interactions the users will have with the ML-enabled system, (e.g., to provide new data for learning, or human-in-the-loop systems where models require human interaction).
<i>Value</i>	the added value as perceived by users from the predictions to their work.
<i>Visualization</i>	how the ML outcomes will be presented so that users can understand them (e.g., specifying dashboard and visualization prototypes for validation).

Infrastructure

ML models produced by data scientists typically are turned into functional and connected systems that demand special characteristics when in operation. The goal of this perspective is to cover the execution of the models, the monitoring of both data and model outputs, and its learning from new data.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Data streaming</i>	what data streaming strategy will be used (e.g., real time data transportation or in batches).
<i>Cost</i>	the financial cost involved with the infrastructure that could affect architectural decisions. Great models can be unusable due to cost to run them and maintain them.
<i>Incremental learning</i>	the need for ML-enabled system abilities to continuously learn from new data, extending the existing model's knowledge.
<i>Integration</i>	the integration that the model will have with the rest of the system functionality (e.g., safety, security, privacy, fairness, legal)
<i>Model serving</i>	how the model of the ML-enabled system will be executed and consumed (e.g., client-side, back-end, cloud-based, web service end-point).
<i>Maintainability</i>	the need to modify ML-enabled systems to improve performance or adapt to a changed environment.
<i>Monitorability</i>	the need to monitor the data and the outputs of the model to alert/detect when data drifts or changes.
<i>Reproducibility</i>	the need to repeatedly run an algorithm/ML process on certain datasets/experiments and obtain the same (or similar) results.
<i>Storage</i>	where the ML artifacts (e.g., models, data, scripts) will be stored.
<i>Telemetry</i>	what ML-enabled system data needs to be collected. Telemetry involves collecting data such as clicks on particular buttons and could involve other usage data.

Model

Building a model implies not only training an algorithm with data to predict some phenomenon. Several other aspects determine its quality.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Algorithm & model selection</i>	the set of algorithms that could be used/investigated, based on the ML problem and other concerns to be considered (e.g., constraints regarding explainability or model performance, for instance, can limit the solution options).
<i>Algorithm parameter tuning</i>	the need to choose a set of optimal hyperparameters for a learning algorithm. A hyperparameter is a parameter whose value is used to control the learning process.
<i>Baseline model</i>	the optional simple model that acts as a reference. Its main function is to contextualize the results of trained models.
<i>Explainability</i>	the need to understand reasons for the model inferences. The model might need to be able to summarize the reasons for its decisions. Other related concerns such as transparency, may apply.
<i>Interpretability</i>	
<i>Inference time</i>	the acceptable time to execute the model and return the predictions.
<i>Input & Output</i>	the expected inputs (features) and outcomes of the model. Of course, the set of meaningful inputs can be refined/improved during pre-processing activities, such as feature selection.
<i>Learning time</i>	the acceptable time to train the model.
<i>Model size</i>	the size of the model in terms of storage and its complexity (e.g., for decision trees there might be needs for pruning).
<i>Performance metrics</i>	the metrics used to evaluate the model (e.g., precision, recall, F1-score, mean square error) and measurable performance expectations.
<i>Performance degradation</i>	the awareness of performance degradation. Over time many models' predictive performance decreases as a given model is tested on new datasets within rapidly evolving environments.

Data

Poor data will result in inaccurate predictions. Hence, ML requires high-quality input data. Based on the Data Quality model defined in the standard ISO/IEC 25012 and our own experience, we elaborate on the data perspective.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
Accuracy	the need to get correct data.
Bias	the need to get data fair samples and representative distributions.
Completeness	the need to get data containing sufficient observations of all situations where the model will operate.
Consistency	the need to get consistent data in a specific context.
Credibility	the need to get true data that is believable and understandable by users.
Data operations	what operations must be applied on the data (e.g., data cleaning and labeling).
Data distribution	the expected data distributions and how data will be split into training, validating and test data.
Data dictionary	the collection of the names, definitions, and attributes for data elements and models.
Data selection	the process of determining the appropriate data type and suitable samples to collect data.
Ethics & privacy	the need to get data to prevent adversely impacting society (e.g., listing potential adverse impacts to be avoided).
Golden dataset	the need for a baseline dataset approved by a domain expert that reflects the problem. It is employed to monitor other data acquired afterwards.
Modeling	what is necessary to convert data in the representation of the model.
Quantity	the expected amount of data according to the type of the problem and the complexity of the algorithm.
Real usage	the need to get real data representing the real problem.
Source	from where the data will be obtained.
Timeliness	the time between when data is expected and when it is readily available for use.

Steps to apply PerSpecML

We expect PerSpecML to be used by requirements engineers to support the specification of ML-enabled systems in collaboration with other stakeholders. The process begins by considering the perspectives. We established an intuitive order to analyze them: ML objectives, user experience, infrastructure, model, and data. Given a perspective, we analyze each concern with the recommended stakeholders, also considering the dependency relationships. If the concern is applicable, we specify it and classify its relevance into desirable, important or essential. The following figure summarizes the steps to apply PerSpecML.

Perspective-Based ML Task and Concern Diagram

Perspective-based ML Specification Template

Please check our interactive Miro board to see the specifications of the *Product classification* Project and the *Mercado* Project. In addition, you can access the Perspective-based ML specification template.

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPcnYrn0=?share_link_id=304092229021